

Rural Development and Urban Planning Administration in Nigeria: A Case Study of Akwa Ibom State

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Abstract

This research sets out to address the problem of rural development and urban planning administration in Nigeria with Akwa Ibom State as a case study. The study adopted a descriptive survey design to elicit unconditional responses from respondents. The three Senatorial Districts of Akwa Ibom State, namely, Akwa Ibom South (Eket), Akwa Ibom West (Uyo) and Akwa Ibom Northwest (Ikot Ekpene), served as reference points for the research. Modernisation Theory by W.W. Rostow (1960) and Parsons (1964) was used. It assumes that “rural areas are underdeveloped because they are traditional and stagnant. Development requires adopting modern technologies, practices, and values.” Public Choice Theory by Charles Tiebout (1956) was also used. It assumes that “urban governance is shaped by individuals acting in their self-interest, as residents 'vote with their feet' by moving to jurisdictions offering preferred services and promoting competition among urban governments for residents and businesses.” Both the primary and secondary methods were adopted in gathering data for the study. A structured questionnaire was used for primary data, while secondary data came from textbooks, journals, newspapers, magazines and government publications. The statistical analyses were based on descriptive statistics or simple percentage tables and chi-square computations. The objective of the study, among others, was to find out whether a deliberate rural development effort can transform the three

Senatorial Districts in Akwa Ibom State into urban centres. Findings showed that a deliberate rural development effort can transform the three Senatorial Districts in Akwa Ibom State into urban centres. Therefore, it was recommended that the Akwa Ibom State Government should be deliberate and intentional in her effort to transform the three Senatorial Districts in Akwa Ibom State to urban centres to enhance speedy development in the state. It was also recommended that the government should adequately fund the Department of Urban Planning for the proper planning and administration of urban centres in the state.

Keywords: Rural Development, Urban, Planning, Administration, Akwa Ibom State

Introduction

Rural development and urban planning administration in Nigeria are twin yet contrasting concepts that remain central to human existence. They are considered opposites in the sense that rural development emphasises local, traditional, and interior advancement within villages or enclaves, whereas urban planning administration denotes a systematic, scientific, and modern process of implementing organised frameworks for the growth of towns and cities.

Both concepts are particularly significant in developing countries such as Nigeria and across Africa and Asia. The essence of rural development is to transform rural areas from their prevailing underdeveloped state into vibrant communities with the features of towns, urban centres, or even cities. Conversely, urban planning seeks to expand and regulate the frontiers of existing towns and cities, ensuring orderly growth into municipalities.

It should be noted that rural and urban planning administration in Nigeria is designed as a course of study for students in the Nigerian universities. This is due to its importance and strategic nature in the Nigerian political landscape. This also underscores the role of planning in human existence. Planning is pivotal to humans, as it is the basis for success in any area of human endeavour. Successful leadership, particularly as it has to do with the administration of rural/urban systems in Nigeria, is dependent on good and adequate planning and execution of such a plan. Other scholars, like FAO (2021) and Hall (2014), have also corroborated the above opinion by stating that planning administration in rural and urban contexts plays a crucial role in ensuring sustainable development, efficient service delivery, and improved living standards.

As a concept of public administration, planning has its general focus. But, within the context of our discussion, while urban planning often focuses on infrastructure, transport, housing, and zoning in densely populated areas, rural planning shifts its emphasis to agricultural development, basic infrastructure, and reducing rural-urban disparities. On the whole, this research critically analyses the administrative mechanisms governing rural and urban planning while also highlighting their divergences or differences, challenges, and convergence. (Luo et al., 2021)

Statement of the Problem

There is a sharp disparity between rural areas and towns or cities, just as there is a similar difference between rural development and urban planning administration in Nigeria. This research was set to address the problem of rural development and urban planning administration in Nigeria using Akwa Ibom State as a case study. In an attempt to achieve this objective, there are a number of challenges that stand in the way of rural development, such as a lack of deliberate rural development efforts, bad or poor road networks, a lack of potable water, an irregular electricity supply, poor healthcare facilities and personnel, dilapidated educational structures, a lack of mechanised agriculture and poor outputs, a lack of sufficient capital, the poor state of rural markets, rural-urban migration, and so forth.

On the other hand, urban planning administration also faces a lot of challenges that impede its rapid growth and expansion. Some of these challenges include a lack of proper planning and administration of urban projects, high population density, vehicular congestion, waste disposal, flooding, pollution, and so forth. It was as a result of the foregoing that this research became necessary to address the aforementioned problems of rural development and urban planning administration in Nigeria, but with emphasis on Akwa Ibom State.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to address the problem of rural development and urban planning administration in Nigeria with Akwa Ibom State as a case study. Whereas, the subsidiary objectives include:

- i. To find out whether a deliberate rural development effort can transform the three (3) Senatorial Districts in Akwa Ibom State into urban centres.
- ii. To verify whether adequate funding of the Department of Urban Planning for the proper planning and administration of urban centres can transform the three (3) Senatorial Districts in Akwa Ibom State into urban centres in the state.

Research Question

Based on the above subsidiary objectives, two research questions were asked to elicit responses from the respondents.

- i. Can a deliberate rural development effort transform the three (3) Senatorial Districts in Akwa Ibom State into urban centres?
- ii. Can adequate funding of the Department of Urban Planning for the proper planning and administration of urban centres transform the three (3) Senatorial Districts in Akwa Ibom State into urban centres in the state?

Research Hypotheses

The researchers postulated two null (H₀) hypotheses to enable statistical computations and calculations.

- i. A deliberate rural development effort may likely not transform the three (3) Senatorial Districts in Akwa Ibom State into urban centres.
- ii. Adequate funding of the Department of Urban Planning for the proper planning and administration of urban centres may most likely not transform the three (3) Senatorial Districts in Akwa Ibom State into urban centres in the state.

Definition of Terms

For clarity purposes, it is expedient to define or operationalise some concepts before going in-depth into this research. Some of those concepts to be defined or operationalised are 'rural', 'urban', 'planning', 'administration', 'planning administration', 'rural planning administration', and 'urban planning administration'.

- I. **Rural:** According to Udoh et al. (2023), “There are many types of environments in which humans live”: rural, urban and suburban. The scholars further posit that the majority of people in the world and in the United States live in urban settings such as cities and suburban neighbourhoods because of the greater number of resources and opportunities afforded to the people there. Despite the rural-urban drift, the authors believe that “a small percentage, however, still live in rural communities around the world.” From the explanation above, the word “rural” can be said to mean “remote, traditional, uncivilised and backward”. By implication, rural communities or people may also refer to remote, traditional, uncivilised and backward communities or people.
- ii. **Urban:** On the contrary, the term “urban” is the antonym or direct opposite of “rural”. In other words, what rural is, urban is not, and vice versa. As stated earlier, the majority of people in the world and in the United States live in urban settings such as cities and suburban neighbourhoods because of the greater number of resources and opportunities afforded to the people there (Udoh et al., 2023). Based on the foregoing, the term “urban” is connected with a town or city. It is the

opposite of rural. An urban centre is a large, civilised and metropolitan centre with a high population density, adequate development and numerous opportunities for citizens to harness. Udoh (2014) identifies urban development as one of the areas that public administration deals with.

- iii. **Planning:** Udoh (2014) sees planning as forecasting. He defines planning as “an act or process of making careful considerations of all the factors and variables that may be involved in a particular action of intent in order to achieve something. According to him, planning requires good quality time. Depending on the size of the project that one is planning, he avers that one does not need to reduce planning only to mental pictures of what one wants to achieve. Good planning needs to be written down; step-by-step strategies for achievement must be shown, and other factors, such as time and resources to be used in achieving the planned project, need to be considered. J.D. Millet and Demock and Demock (cited separately in Naidu, 2011) define planning as “the process of determining the objectives of administrative effort and of devising the means calculated to achieve them”. On the other hand, “planning is clarifying one's objectives and determining what action shall be taken by whom, when. By what method, and at what costs, in order to achieve the desired goals”. Therefore, “planning is an important managerial activity.”
- iv. **Administration:** There are as many definitions of administration as there are scholars. Despite their divergent viewpoints, one thing is common about administration: it is a tool or mechanism for carrying out office activities. In his first and second editions, Udoh (2014) and (2024) recognised the importance and the critical role that administration plays in human affairs. Apart from admiring Luther Gulick and Lyndall Urwick's presumption in their “Papers on the Science of Administration” that “administration is administration, wherever it is found”, the author also cited Pfiffner and Prethus (1967) as defining administration as “the coordination of collective effort to implement public policy”. That is, a collective affair involving many people, which should profit the majority of the people.”
- v. **Planning Administration:** Planning administration is the same as administration of planning. By administration of planning, Udoh (2014) and Udoh (2024), respectively, assert that it “has to do with the ways, methods and principles with which planning is carried out”. In a nutshell, you may plan, and your plan will amount to nothing because it is a dormant plan. A plan can only produce results when administered. Therefore, planning administration or administration of planning becomes very important in executing government policies, programmes or projects. In rural/urban planning administration in Nigeria, planning administration or administration of planning are key concepts.

- vi. **Rural Planning Administration:** As stated above, there are key concepts in rural/urban planning administration in Nigeria, including planning administration or administration of planning. There is no way rural communities can evolve to become urban centres except individuals and/or governments agree to carry out some rural planning administration. Going by Okereke et al.'s (2010) and Uma Lele's (1998) definitions of rural development, as cited in Udoh (2020), the former opines that "rural development is urban development of some sort." But, in the latter's opinion, rural development is seen as "improving the living standards of the masses of the low-income population residing in rural areas". However, even though the author is in total agreement with the fact that, "given all the characteristics of urban areas in the rural communities, the latter will be transformed into the status of the former." According to Okereke et al. (2010), the authors embrace Lele's definition more in this context since it has enumerated practical action plans/steps for the administration of rural areas. Such administrative parameters include: (1) aiming at improving the living standards of the low-income population to imply that rural development must involve **mobilisation** of the people and resources in order to improve production capacity and output; (2) mass participation of those in the low-income brackets and the few wealthy ones, which first and foremost calls for their **involvement in the development process**, after being fully informed of what the government wants to do in their areas, before being trained, educated and empowered to secure those projects in those areas; and (3) the desire to make the process self-sufficient. This implies that manpower, capacity and workforce must be created among the people in order to **guarantee self-sustenance, maintenance and security** of the projects in their various areas when handed over to the communities by the government. The second parameter actually corroborates what community development represents, which, according to Akpabio et al. (2023), refers to "a process where community members come together to take collective action and generate collective solutions to a common problem."
- vii. **Urban Planning Administration:** Urban planning administration in Nigeria may differ from rural planning administration in various ways, since urban is the opposite of rural. In this sense, the implication of Okereke et al.'s (2010) definition cited in Udoh (2020) holds that "given all the characteristics of urban areas in the rural communities, the latter will be transformed into the status of the former." In other words, the presence of a high population, electricity, portable water, schools, healthcare centres, good roads, transportation systems, telecommunication, etc. are some of such characteristics that make up urban centres. These amenities are lacking in the rural communities. From time-to-time government plans administer these amenities in the urban centres across the nation. To administer means to

execute. Therefore, the execution of the government's projects and programmes by the executives is the administration of planning the urban centres. The presence of these amenities in the urban centres is the reason that Udoh et al. (2023) earlier posited, "The majority of people in the world and in the United States live in urban settings such as cities and suburban neighbourhoods because of the greater number of resources and opportunities afforded to the people there."

Theoretical Framework

Two theories, each representing rural development and urban planning administration, respectively, were adopted in this research.

First and foremost, Modernisation Theory, propounded by W.W. Rostow in 1960 and Parsons in 1964, was used. It assumes that "rural areas are underdeveloped because they are traditional and stagnant. Development requires adopting modern technologies, practices, and values" (Rostow, 1960).

Secondly, Public Choice Theory, as espoused by Charles Tiebout in 1956, was also used. It assumes that "urban governance is shaped by individuals acting in their self-interest. Residents 'vote with their feet' by moving to jurisdictions offering preferred services. Promotes competition among urban governments for residents and businesses" (Mills, 1956).

Methodology

This study employed a descriptive survey design within a case study framework to obtain unbiased responses from participants. Both primary and secondary sources of data were utilised. For the primary data, proportional stratified random sampling was adopted to ensure fair representation of the relevant subgroups. A structured questionnaire served as the principal instrument for data collection. The questionnaire was designed with both closed-ended and demographic items. The closed-ended questions employed a five-point Likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (U), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD), to measure respondents' perceptions. The demographic section captured information such as age, gender, educational background, marital status, and employment status.

Secondary data were obtained from textbooks, journal articles, government publications, newspapers, and magazines. These sources provided documentary evidence and background information that complemented the primary data. The use of existing records followed an ex post facto research approach, which allowed the study to analyse past events and conditions in order to identify their implications for the present research problem.

The population of the study comprised individuals drawn from the Ministry of Rural Development and Cooperatives, the Department of Urban Planning, and residents from the three senatorial districts of Akwa Ibom State: Akwa Ibom South (Eket), Akwa Ibom West (Uyo), and Akwa Ibom North-West (Ikot Ekpene). A proportional stratified random sampling technique was used to ensure that participants from each stratum were adequately represented. Altogether, 804 respondents formed the sample size for the research, and each was administered the same set of questions, written in simple English to aid comprehension. To preserve anonymity and facilitate analysis, respondents were coded as follows: A – Ministry of Rural Development and Cooperatives; B – Department of Urban Planning; C – Akwa Ibom South (Eket Senatorial District); D – Akwa Ibom West (Uyo Senatorial District); and E – Akwa Ibom North-West (Ikot Ekpene Senatorial District)

Out of 400 questionnaire copies initially distributed, 345 were properly completed and retrieved, while 55 were either damaged or inadequately filled and therefore excluded from the analysis. The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics, specifically simple percentage tables, to test the research hypotheses. In addition, the analytical method was employed to examine the extent to which deviations of observed frequencies from expected or theoretical frequencies were statistically significant. This combination of approaches ensured that the results were both reliable and valid for addressing the objectives of the study.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 1: Sample Size:

Code	Establishment	Questionnaire Administered	Questionnaire Lost	Questionnaire Retrieved	Questionnaire (%)
A	Ministry of Rural Development and Cooperatives	80	6	74	21.45
B	Department of Urban Planning	80	9	71	20.58
C	Akwa Ibom South (Eket Senatorial District)	80	12	68	19.71
D	Akwa Ibom West (Uyo Senatorial District)	80	17	63	18.26

E	Akwa Ibom Northwest (Ikot Ekpene Senatorial District).	80	11	69	20
Total		400	55	345	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Interpretation:

The simple percentage formula for calculating the above table is as follow:

$$\text{Percentage (\%)} = \frac{\text{Response Rate (Q. Retrieved)} \times 100}{\text{Total Response Rate}} = \text{Percentage (\%)}$$

Example A: $74 \times 100 = 7400$
 $7400/345 = 21.45$

A total of 400 questionnaire forms were produced and evenly distributed across the five categories, with 80 copies each allocated to groups A–E. From this distribution, the Ministry of Rural Development and Cooperatives lost 6 forms and successfully retrieved 74, representing 21.45 percent of the valid responses. The Department of Urban Planning lost 9 forms, resulting in 71 retrieved, which accounted for 20.58 percent. Akwa Ibom South (Eket Senatorial District) lost 12 forms and retrieved 68, representing 19.71 percent. Akwa Ibom West (Uyo Senatorial District) lost 17 forms, yielding 63 valid responses, representing 18.26 percent. Finally, Akwa Ibom North-West (Ikot Ekpene Senatorial District) recorded a loss of 11 forms, with 69 retrieved, representing 20.00 percent.

Table 2: Rate of Total Number of Questionnaire Administered and Retrieved

Code	Establishment	Questionnaire Administered	Questionnaire Retrieved	Questionnaire (%)
A	Ministry of Rural Development and Cooperatives	80	74	21.45
B	Department of Urban Planning	80	71	20.58
C	Akwa Ibom South (Eket Senatorial District)	80	68	19.71
D	Akwa Ibom West (Uyo Senatorial District)	80	63	18.26
E	Akwa Ibom North west (Ikot Ekpene Senatorial District).	80	69	20
Total Response Rate		400	345	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

From Table 2, it is observed that, apart from the fourth column, which originally represented “Questionnaires Lost” and has been removed in this arrangement, all other variables remain consistent with Table 1. Accordingly, the Ministry of Rural Development and Cooperatives recorded 74 valid respondents, representing 21.45 percent of the total questionnaires retrieved. The Department of Urban Planning had 71 respondents, accounting for 20.58 percent. Akwa Ibom South (Eket Senatorial District) returned 68 questionnaires, representing 19.71 percent. Akwa Ibom West (Uyo Senatorial District) retrieved 63 questionnaires, which constituted 18.26 percent, while Akwa Ibom North-West (Ikot Ekpene Senatorial District) had 69 respondents, representing 20.00 percent.

Conclusion/Recommendations

This study set out to examine the issues surrounding rural development and urban planning administration in Nigeria, with specific focus on Akwa Ibom State. Findings from the analysis, based on simple percentage distributions, revealed that the Ministry of Rural Development and Cooperatives accounted for 74 respondents, representing 21.45 percent of the total valid questionnaires retrieved. The Department of Urban Planning had 71 respondents, representing 20.58 percent. Akwa Ibom South (Eket Senatorial District) returned 68 questionnaires, representing 19.71 percent, while Akwa Ibom West (Uyo Senatorial District) accounted for 63 respondents, representing 18.26 percent. Finally, Akwa Ibom North-West (Ikot Ekpene Senatorial District) had 69 respondents, representing 20.00 percent. These distributions demonstrate a fairly balanced representation across the studied groups, thereby enhancing the reliability of the findings.

The implications of these findings are significant. First, the relatively even spread of responses suggests that both rural and urban stakeholders share concerns about development planning and administration in the state. This balance highlights the interdependence of rural development and urban planning, showing that policies in one sphere inevitably affect the other. Second, the slightly higher representation from the Ministry of Rural Development and Cooperatives points to the continued relevance of rural development in shaping socioeconomic outcomes, even within a rapidly urbanising state. Third, the close distribution among the three senatorial districts indicates that challenges relating to rural–urban development are not isolated but cut across different geographical zones, underscoring the need for state-wide strategies rather than piecemeal interventions.

In practical terms, these results imply that policymakers in Akwa Ibom State and Nigeria as a whole should pursue an integrated approach to rural development and urban planning. Strengthening institutional capacity in both ministries and ensuring

coordination across senatorial districts would enhance service delivery, resource allocation, and long-term sustainability. Moreover, since the findings demonstrate a shared stake among diverse respondents, inclusive planning processes that capture voices from both rural and urban communities are essential. Such an approach will not only bridge development gaps but also promote balanced growth, reduce rural–urban migration pressures, and improve the overall quality of life for citizens.

Based on the foregoing, it was recommended that:

- i. The Akwa Ibom State Government should be deliberate and intentional in her effort to transform the three (3) Senatorial Districts in Akwa Ibom State to urban centres to enhance speedy development in the state.
- ii. The state government should adequately fund the Department of Urban Planning for the proper planning and administration of urban centres in the state.

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